

TEACH MORE, EARN MORE: EMPLOYEES' JOB DESCRIPTION AND THEIR SALARY AT ICCBI

Gheera May M. Gonzales¹, Jhino Paul C. Abellar², Angelo B. Castillo³, Joana Mizyl P. Arellano⁴, Shania Lizette A. Atienza⁵, Jowenie A. Mangarin⁶

¹²³⁴⁵⁶ Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc., Plaza Mabini, 4213, Balayan, Batangas, Philippines

Corresponding Emails: mail@iccbalayan.edu.ph

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Abstract

This study examines the correlation between job descriptions and salaries at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc. (ICCB), a private Catholic institution devoted to faith-based education. Using qualitative research, a single-case study was conducted with ten (10) participants selected through purposive sampling based on specific criteria. Through face-to-face interviews, data was collected and analyzed using a narrative approach. Thus, it was found out that job descriptions at ICCBI are established through methods like job analysis, role and responsibility approaches, qualifications, and the school manual-based method. Salary determination involves factors such as tenure, educational attainment, performance, teaching loads, experience, and collegial care. Key factors influencing job descriptions include salary differentiation, aligned job descriptions, career development opportunities, and increased duties and responsibilities. Variations in the salary structure are affected by teaching loads, department designations, and educational qualifications. The findings indicate that job descriptions impact employee salaries at the institution, and future research is encouraged to explore identified factors for insights into developing more efficient roles and contributing to organizational effectiveness. With this, the study proposed a strategic plan for future use and implementation.

Keywords: *Job descriptions, Salaries, Immaculate Conception College (ICCB), Strategic plan*

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Introduction

Workplace dynamics and technology breakthroughs have experienced substantial modifications in our time today, requiring a thorough re-evaluation of job descriptions. The issue of equitable compensation attracted considerable attention from scholars and practitioners, who consistently emphasized the substantial impact of salary structures on workforce motivation and productivity (Kraus et al., 2023).

According to Department Order No. 18-A, Series of 2011, salaries, defined as regular payments by employers for labor, were typically disbursed on a monthly basis. These payments could vary based on factors such as promotions or changes in working hours outlined in employment contracts. Beyond the fundamental nature of salaries, employers often augment compensation packages with additional benefits, including paid time off, health insurance, and travel bonuses. Understanding the intricacies of salaries was crucial for fostering employee engagement, with these financial considerations influenced by industry supply and demand, as noted by Vallikat (2023), who described salary as a fixed, regular payment from employers to employees.

Job descriptions, as underscored by Jacobson et al. (2013), played a pivotal role in the employment relationship, serving as comprehensive written explanations of tasks, procedures, and justifications for specific roles. Formal organizations, such as Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc., utilized job descriptions to delineate responsibilities within divisions, ultimately fostering clarity and efficiency. Established in 1935, this private Catholic school placed a high value on faith-based education and prioritized experienced staff, supported by diocesan funds, student tuition, and fundraising efforts (Otto, 2015).

In the contemporary workplace, the connection between employees' job descriptions and their corresponding salaries is deemed crucial for organizational success. Discussions on effective human resource management centralized around the intricate aspects of job design and compensation structures, all in the pursuit of attracting and retaining top talent. Findings from the 2013 WorldatWork survey suggested that organizations strategically aligning job descriptions with competitive salary packages demonstrated higher employee satisfaction and retention rates. Despite this recognized significance, a notable research gap existed, indicating the need for further investigation.

While existing studies explored the general association between job descriptions and compensation, a more thorough analysis was required to understand the nuanced factors influencing this relationship. The evolving nature of job roles, shaped by technological advancements, changing organizational structures, and shifting employee expectations, implies that traditional models of job evaluation and compensation may no longer adequately capture the complexities of contemporary work environments. The research gap lay in the absence of recent, in-depth examinations that considered the multifaceted dimensions of job roles and their direct impact on salary structures.

This research strove to bridge that gap by emphasizing how job descriptions intricately influenced salaries. Drawing insights from relevant literature and studies, the aim was to provide a nuanced understanding of the dynamic relationship between job descriptions and salaries in today's ever-evolving work landscape, offering practical insights for organizations seeking to navigate these complexities effectively.

Statement of the Problems

This study focused on understanding how job descriptions and salaries interact at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc. The key questions it aimed to answer were:

1. How are job descriptions defined and documented for employees at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc.?
2. What factors influence the determination of salaries for employees at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc., and to what extent do these factors relate to their job descriptions?
3. Are there variations in salary structures based on employees' job descriptions, experience, or other relevant factors within the institution?

4. How does the alignment between job descriptions and salaries impact job satisfaction and retention among the faculty and staff of Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc.?
5. What best practices or recommendations can be derived from the study to ensure a fair and transparent relationship between job descriptions and salaries within faith-based educational organizations?

Methodology

To achieve the research goal of examining how job descriptions affect salaries at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc., the study used a qualitative research approach based on Hughes's (2016) suggestion to explore teachers' salary structures and responsibilities. Following this advice, the research adopted a qualitative design, specifically employing a single case study. This choice was intentional, aiming for a detailed exploration of employees' real-life experiences at the institution. Focusing on a single case study aligned with the primary objective of fully understanding how job descriptions directly impact salaries at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc. This approach allowed for a nuanced examination of the complex relationship between job descriptions and salary dynamics, providing valuable insights into the specific context of the institution being studied.

Population and Sampling

The researchers used purposeful sampling, also called judgmental sampling, which is a non-probability technique. This method was chosen to narrow down the target group and ensure a specific number of participants within that demographic. The study focused on ten (10) teachers from Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc. For teachers to be included in the survey and interview phases, they had to meet specific criteria: (a) being employed as full-time or part-time teachers at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc.; (b) having a length of service of five (5) years or more; and (c) handling two (2) or more teaching loads or responsibilities within the institution. This careful and purposeful selection process aimed to gather insights from teachers with significant experience and varied responsibilities, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the study's focus.

Instrumentations

To explore the impact of job descriptions on employee salaries at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc., a semi-structured interview tool was developed. This instrument was administered to ten (10) participants chosen through purposive sampling. The questions were crafted to investigate participants' views and experiences regarding how job descriptions influence their salaries. Before distribution, the instrument underwent validation by three experts, and necessary revisions were incorporated.

Data Collection

The research began with a thorough review of the research instrument to ensure clarity, relevance, and appropriateness for data collection. Validation from experts was sought to enhance the instrument's credibility. Their feedback was used to refine the instrument for optimal reliability and validity. Then, formal permission for research access was obtained from Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc., securing ethical clearance and authorization to proceed. After receiving approval from school administrators, participants were informed, and face-to-face interviews were conducted. The data was manually processed and analyzed in narrative form to align with the study's objectives and answer the research questions accurately. Then, a strategic plan was created for the benefit of the participating locale and future use.

Data Analysis

To achieve the research goals of understanding how job descriptions impact employee salaries at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc., a narrative analysis approach was chosen. This qualitative method involves systematically examining and interpreting stories or narratives. By focusing on individual stories within the research

group, this approach helped uncover central narratives. Analyzing participants' detailed accounts allowed for the extraction of meaningful insights and patterns, contributing to a comprehensive exploration of the research question.

Ethical Consideration

Obtaining informed consent was crucial for individuals to join the study. This meant providing detailed information to ensure participants understood the study's implications, allowing them to decide freely without pressure. Participants could withdraw at any time, and their privacy and anonymity were protected. Measures were taken to keep their identities and shared information confidential. Objectivity and neutrality were maintained in interactions and analyses to ensure unbiased findings. Adhering to these ethical standards was essential for conducting a respectful study that prioritized participants' well-being and autonomy.

Results and Discussions

Presented below are the significant findings and data analysis acquired from the responses of the 10 (ten) participants of the study.

Table 1

Process of defining and documenting job description at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc.

Themes	Excerpts
Job Analysis	"Job description is a set of responsibilities and duties you need to do in an institution as a teacher as stated by P1 and P2. Additionally, P9 emphasizes that job description begins with a distinct job title, followed by outlining the job's purpose or objectives, specifying the tasks involved, detailing the job requirements, and providing information on compensation and benefits."
Role and Responsibility Method	"P3 and P5 point out that job description is defined and documented by giving the roles and responsibilities of each position. Moreover, job description are normally developed and documented as a teacher of this institution, ICCBI through a careful procedures that assures clarity, correctness and connection with educational institutions aim and objective, specified by P9."
Qualifications and Credential	"P4 and P6 indicates that job descriptions are defined based in a teacher's attainments and tenures, along with their experiences."
School Manual Based Method	"Job description is taken from the faculty handbook as mentioned by P10."
Uncertainty and Lack of Knowledge	"As per P7 said, I'm honestly not sure."

Job Analysis

P1 and P2 highlighted that a job description was being determined by looking at the set of responsibilities and roles for teachers. It emphasized the duties and roles expected of them. In addition, P9 mentioned the key components of job descriptions, including a clear job title, objectives, task lists, job requirements, and compensation details.

"Start with a clear job title; next is the job purpose or objectives; a list of tasks; the requirements of the job; and including the salary and benefits," affirmed P9.

The document detailing the job description delineates the tasks and activities undertaken by an employee. This marks the initial phase of job descriptions, emphasizing solely the work tasks and activities (Hawkes &

Weathington, 2014). Furthermore, the job description for the third generation encompasses the distinct roles within the organization, including factors such as attitude, enthusiasm, teamwork capabilities, skill enhancement, and the employees' contributions to workplace enhancements (Baker, 2016). A job description is a list of tasks, obligations, and responsibilities required for a job.

Role and Responsibility Method

P3, P5, and P8 indicated that job descriptions were created by outlining the roles and responsibilities associated with each position. This process ensured clarity and alignment with the educational institution's objectives.

"Job descriptions are normally developed and documented as a teacher of this institution, ICCBI, through careful procedures that assure clarity, correctness, and connection with educational institutions aim and objectives," as stated by P8.

A job description is an official document created by an employer with the objective of defining the scope of an employee's role and the expected tasks they are to undertake. These documents serve the purpose of outlining job duties, responsibilities, and specifications, as well as the necessary knowledge, skills, abilities, and other attributes required to fulfill the job requirements (Carliner et al., 2015). Moreover, the job description ought to comprise a brief summary outlining essential aspects of the position. This summary may encompass key responsibilities, functions, and duties, as well as education and experience prerequisites, along with any other relevant details (Ayers, 2015).

Qualifications and Credentials

P4 and P6 stressed the influence of a teacher's experience and tenure in shaping job descriptions. This implied that the descriptions were tailored to individual backgrounds and qualifications.

"Job descriptions are defined based on a teacher's attainments and tenures, along with their experiences," as said by P4 and P6.

Organizational tenure is characterized as the duration an individual has been associated with an organization, fostering a meaningful connection between the employee and the organization, and encouraging positive employee behaviors (Manag, 2013). Additionally, the recruitment of teachers stands out as a pivotal responsibility for principals, yet the connection between a principal's tenure in a school and their effectiveness in hiring teachers with lasting commitment remains unclear. Both teacher retention and principal experience are crucial factors influencing the stability of a school (Guthery and Bailes, 2022).

School Manual-Based Method

P10 stated that job descriptions were derived from the faculty handbook, suggesting an official source for these documents.

"The job description is taken from the faculty handbook," as mentioned by P10.

The principal's responsibility involves leading and overseeing the planning, delivery, assessment, and enhancement of education for all students in a community. This is achieved through the strategic allocation of resources provided by both the department and the school community. A crucial aspect of this role is to enhance the knowledge of teachers within the school regarding student learning and effective teaching practices (Roles and Responsibilities Teaching Service, 2017, Victoria State Government).

Additionally, school administrators must possess a comprehensive understanding of the manual, and adherence to the specified policies and procedures is essential to maintaining uniform testing conditions state-wide (New York State Testing Program: English Language and Arts and Mathematics Test, 2023, New York State Education Department).

Uncertainty and Lack of Knowledge

The participant 7 conveyed a notable sense of uncertainty and acknowledged a deficiency in specific knowledge regarding the intricacies of job description definition processes. This uncertainty was explicitly articulated when P7 stated, "I'm honestly not sure." This expression indicates a level of hesitancy or lack of confidence in understanding the nuances associated with the formulation of job descriptions. The participant's candid admission suggests a perceived gap in their knowledge, emphasizing the need for further exploration and clarification on the subject matter. The acknowledgment of uncertainty by P7 serves as a valuable insight into the participant's perspective and highlights a potential area for improvement or focus in the context of job description-related processes.

Table 2

Factors in the establishment of salaries for employees at ICCBI

Themes	Excerpts
Tenure and Service Duration	"According to P1, P2, and P6 tenure is a factor influencing the determination of salary as a teacher in ICCBI."
Educational Attainments	As indicated by P4 and P9, factors such as academic credentials and educational qualifications impact the determination of teachers' salaries at ICCBI.
Performance and Professional Growth	"Derived from P2 and P8, factors such as professional development and performance assessment play a role in deciding the salary for educators at ICCBI."
Teaching Loads and Department	"According to P3, P7, and P8, the number of teaching loads influences the determination of salary. Additionally, P8 emphasized that the work environment and performance evaluation also play a role in salary determination."
Experience and Experience Based Increment	"As per P5 said, experience, since before I entered ICC, I was an IT Consultant so my experience from that post is related to my job as a teacher here in ICC. Along with P9 said, the teachers with Master's degree can be assigned to teach more specialized or advanced courses."
Collegial Care and Consideration	"Care of Faculty, highlighted by P10."

Tenure and Service Duration

P1, P2, and P6 had highlighted the significance of tenure or years in service as a key determinant of salary. This theme underscored the notion that the longer an employee had served, the more likely they were to receive a higher salary.

"Years in service, professional growth, and moderatorship or other assignments," said P2.

The longer an employee remains with a company, the higher their gross salary tends to be, as indicated by Priya in 2020. Firms are inclined to offer increased wages to employees with more experience. Furthermore, according to Caplin et al. (2022), a newly hired employee lacking relevant experience may receive a comparatively lower salary, especially if the job demands more tenure to achieve peak productivity. Despite being viewed as a potential source of inefficiency, tenure can serve as a significant incentive for both employers and employees to invest in high-quality

employment and stimulate enhanced performance, as noted by Eurofound in 2019. Tenure, often criticized for possibly diminishing employee efforts, inflating wages, and undermining competitiveness, is argued to provide job security, fostering higher organizational commitment and engagement, as supported by studies from Furåker & Berglund (2014) and Getahun Asfaw & Chang (2019).

Educational Attainments

P4 and P9 stated that educational qualifications and academic degrees were identified as contributing factors to determining salary. This theme suggested that higher levels of education could lead to higher compensation.

P4 and P9 highlighted that "academic degree and educational qualifications are factors influencing the determination of salary as a teacher in ICCBI."

Higher levels of educational achievement are associated with higher earnings, reduced unemployment rates, improved health, and various other social and economic advantages, as indicated by Sisaket in 2022. Over the past few decades, individuals with a college degree or higher have experienced a consistent increase in earnings, contrasting with those with lower educational levels who have encountered stagnant or declining wages. Additionally, the lifetime earnings of individuals holding a college degree are nearly twice as substantial as those without one, as highlighted by Broady and Hershbein in 2020.

Performance and professional growth

P2 and P8 mentioned that performance evaluation and professional growth, including achievements like moderatorship or other assignments, were mentioned as factors that impacted salary decisions. This indicated that merit-based recognition and career progression could influence compensation.

"Years in service, professional growth, and moderatorship or other assignments," stated P8.

Linking pay to performance is considered equitable for employees, grounded in the notion that those who contribute more value through their work or projects should receive greater compensation or benefits. Although this principle seems straightforward, its practical application can be challenging. Performance assessment is often a complex task. Further, the connection between extrinsic rewards, such as bonuses, and employee motivation is not always straightforward, as highlighted by Desai in 2019. Similarly, advancing in your career can lead to an increase in salary, contributing to greater financial well-being. Career growth plays a crucial role in realizing your full potential by encouraging the pursuit of new opportunities rather than remaining stagnant (Wool, 2022).

Teaching Loads and Department

P3, P7, and P8 had asserted that the number of teaching loads and the department were identified as factors affecting salary. The workload and the specific teaching assignments within the college were considered relevant factors.

"As a teacher of ICCBI, several factors influence the determination of our salary, like subject loading, work environment, and performance evaluation," as described by P8.

In accordance with Hart and Staveland, as cited in Tarwaka et al. (2015), workload emerges from the interplay among task demands, the working environment (utilized as a workplace), and the skills, attitudes, and perceptions of workers. Operationally, workload is at times defined based on factors like the demands of tasks or the efforts invested in completing them. Additionally, academic departments (or schools) attribute varying relative weights to the significance of faculty roles in teaching, research, and service. These weights play a crucial role in decisions regarding promotions, tenure, and annual salary increments. Furthermore, they influence the choices of prospective faculty members when considering appointments within the departments. It is presumed that elevating the weight assigned to teaching in comparison to research and service would motivate faculty to enhance both the quantity and quality of time dedicated to teaching (Harter et al., 2015).

Experience and Experience-Based Increment

P5 and P9 highlighted experience as directly associated with determining salary. This suggested that the college might have implemented experience-based salary increments.

"The factors that determine my salary as a teacher are my experiences," as per P5.

There exists a clear correlation between age and salary, with most individuals witnessing a simultaneous increase in both as they acquire new skills, accumulate experience, and expand their potential, according to Juanita in 2019. Notably, instructional methods centered on courses are more advantageous, as they are linked to enhanced independent thinking and meaningful engagement in tasks, as highlighted by Graves in 2021. Furthermore, the presence of pertinent industry experience can impact the upward trajectory of salary increments.

Collegial Care and Consideration

P10 mentioned that faculty members had the say when determining salaries. This theme reflected a humanistic and supportive approach, "Care of Faculty," as pointed out by P10.

The degree to which employees collaborate and get along with others is denoted as collegiality (Su et al., 2022). Studies indicate that increased collegiality is associated with additional positive behaviors outside of regular job duties, such as organizational citizenship behavior, where employees go beyond their job descriptions to assist colleagues (Miles et al., 2015). Many contemporary organizations adopt an organic structure where collegiality is crucial for achieving heightened performance. In a collegial system, decision-making responsibility is vested in teachers, professors, and faculty board members (Sahli and Zetterquist, 2016).

Table 3

Effects of the identified factors to job descriptions of the employees

Themes	Excerpts
Salary Differentiation	P1 said, since I am a grade schoolteacher, our rate is the lowest in the institution. Supported by P2, as a tenured teacher, we are expecting that our salary is higher than the new ones in terms of service, but since what we are handling is the elementary, we have the lowest rate in the institution. As specified by P3, the more teaching loads given to a teacher, the higher his/her salary could be. However, P4 mention that I'm a fairly new addition to the faculty/staff, therefore, my salary is levelled on the lower part of the grid based on the employees' average salaries. P5 indicates too that experience, since before I entered ICC, I was an IT Consultant so my experience from that post is related to my job as a teacher here in ICC. P6 illustrates that I know well enough my duties and responsibilities as a SHS teacher and secretary.
Appropriate and Aligned Job Descriptions	As per P5, I was an IT Consultant so my experience from that post is related to my job as a teacher here in ICC. According to P6, I know well enough my duties and responsibilities as a SHS teacher and secretary.
Career Development Opportunities	As mentioned by P8, it is directly affecting my career as a teacher because it taken into account when selecting assignments and professional growth. However P9 said that the teachers with Master's degree can be assigned to teach more specialized or advanced courses.
Bigger Duties and Responsibilities	As explained by P7, all the factors relate to the entire job description.

Salary Differentiation

P1 and P2 highlighted the relationship between the type of teaching position (e.g., grade school vs. other levels) and salary. They noted that the nature of the role influenced the compensation, with some roles earning lower rates in the institution. P3 also noted that the number of teaching loads assigned to a teacher had a direct impact on their salary. This suggested that workload played a role in compensation determination. Moreover, P4, P5, and P6 discussed the influence of tenure and experience on their job descriptions and salaries. Those with more experience expected higher compensation, while newer additions may have started at lower levels.

“As a tenured teacher, we are expecting that our salary is higher than the new ones in terms of service, but since what we are handling is the elementary we have the lowest rate in the institution”, in accordance with P2.

“The more teaching loads given to a teacher, the higher his/her salary could be”, as specified by P3.

On the word of P5, “experience, since before I entered ICC, I was an IT Consultant so my experience from that post is related to my job as a teacher here in ICC.”

Public schools establish restrictions on teacher workload, delineating maximum hours and work periods for teaching and preparation (Botes, 2023). Teaching unions within public schools also have the ability to negotiate adjustments to teacher workload and secure guaranteed salary increases. In contrast, the workload for teachers tends to be higher in charter schools. The variance in pay scales between public and private school teachers can be attributed to differences in work environments. Public schools, with larger student populations and larger class sizes, operate under strict government policies and standards, catering to a diverse student body. On the other hand, private school teachers may encounter smaller class sizes, more autonomy, and opportunities for specialization, potentially influencing their compensation (Krosel, et al., 2023). Furthermore, a distinct factor affecting the pay disparity is the absence of collective bargaining agreements for most private school teachers, as revealed in a recent survey by a teachers' organization (Chi, 2023). The survey found that, in general, private school teachers earn less than their counterparts in public schools.

Workload standards for educators are outlined in Law No. 14 of 2005 for teachers and lecturers. Article 35 specifies the key responsibilities of teachers, encompassing activities such as lesson planning, conducting instructional sessions, evaluating learning outcomes, guiding and training students, and fulfilling additional duties. Relatedly, teacher performance is a nuanced outcome influenced by various factors, both internal and external. Internal factors stem from within the teacher and can impact their capabilities, skills, personality, perception, motivation to teach, work experience, and family background (Utami & Negara, 2021).

Extended tenure commonly results in increased expertise and knowledge within your profession. As an employee with a longer tenure, there is a usual dedication to expanding existing skills, acquiring new ones, and a willingness to undergo cross-training. Employers may find it advantageous to impart new skills, fostering enhanced confidence and qualifications beneficial for current and prospective roles (Birt, 2023).

Appropriate and Aligned Job Descriptions

P5 emphasized that prior experience as an IT Consultant was related to the job description as a teacher. This highlighted the importance of relevant experience in defining job roles. In addition, P6 mentioned that familiarity with duties and responsibilities, gained through years of experience, was related to job descriptions. This suggested that experience contributed to a deeper understanding of one's role.

“Since I’m working at ICC for 6 years, I know well enough my duties and responsibilities as a SHS teacher and secretary”, as mentioned by P6.

Collaboration between Human Resources and hiring managers is crucial to accurately craft and align job descriptions with the real, day-to-day responsibilities of employees, as emphasized by Williams (2022). Furthermore, hands-on experience plays a pivotal role in professional development, enabling individuals to showcase their skills to potential employers while gaining insights into their chosen field. It serves as a valuable tool for individuals to recognize their strengths and areas for improvement, aiding them in making informed professional decisions, as highlighted by Scharpf (2019). The significance of defining roles and responsibilities extends beyond merely finding the right candidate for a job. It also enhances the overall employee experience and contributes to the operational efficiency of the organization, as noted by Rose (2021).

When duties and obligations are clearly outlined, it enhances employees' focus and facilitates increased productivity. Improved teamwork and collaboration among team members result from the avoidance of duplicated efforts or interference with each other's tasks. Precisely defined roles also facilitate efficient task delegation, ensuring that assignments are given to individuals with the most relevant skills and expertise. Furthermore, the clarity regarding roles and responsibilities ensures that everyone understands their expectations and comprehends how their work contributes to the organization's overarching objectives. This absence of confusion or ambiguity enables individuals to concentrate on their areas of expertise and make meaningful contributions (Dinna, 2023).

Career Development Opportunities

P8 suggested that factors related to job descriptions, such as experience, played a direct role in career development, influencing assignments and professional growth. Thus, P9 pointed out that teachers with a Master's degree might have been assigned to teach more specialized or advanced courses. This underscored the role of educational qualifications in defining job descriptions.

"The teachers with Master's degree can be assigned to teach more specialized or advanced courses", said by P9.

Attaining a master's degree provides teachers with an advanced and intricate comprehension of their chosen subject. Moreover, it enhances educators' teaching proficiency, leading to improved average test scores and increased graduation rates. Additionally, the pursuit of a master's degree in education offers valuable hands-on experience that can be applied directly in the classroom. This includes the acquisition of practical skills within a supervised classroom setting and the opportunity to experiment with diverse teaching environments, instructing various groups such as children, adults, and students with special needs. Furthermore, obtaining a master's degree in education allows individuals to establish expertise and credibility within their field, as highlighted by Llego (2014).

Bigger Duties and Responsibilities

P7 suggested that the identified factors related to the entire job description, indicating that various elements, such as salary, experience, and assignments, collectively contributed to defining the role.

"It relate to the entire job description", as said by P7.

Establish the groundwork for continuous performance management. Clearly defining role duties and responsibilities simplifies the assessment of new employees' success and ensures the attainment of specific targets. Additionally, it aids employees in formulating personal goals for progression within their current role. Moreover, job descriptions not only acquaint potential candidates with their prospective roles but also encourage them to contemplate how they can enhance those responsibilities, adding greater value to the organization. Furthermore, delineate boundaries regarding employee responsibilities. This practice ensures that both new and existing team members do not exceed the scope of what they are compensated for. Additionally, substantiate an employee's compensation. By itemizing all duties and requirements, you provide a context for understanding why a particular role is remunerated in a specific manner (Carver, 2021).

Table 4

Variations in salary structure and factors that affect it

Themes	Excerpts
Teaching Loads as a Key Factor	Based on P1, the salary is depends upon with the teaching loads he/she have. In accordance P2 stated that, if the teacher has many teaching load the teacher will receive good compensation/salary. Supported by P3, teaching loads affects the salary. P4 agreed that t is depends where department you are in and the teaching loads. Assisted backed by P6 that it is based on the teaching loads you have. As well as back up by P9 saying it is based on the teaching loads. Moreover P10 agreed that it is based on the teaching loads.
Department Designation	As explained by P4, it is depends where department you are in.
Educational Qualifications and Tenure	From the point of view of P5, it depends on academic qualification, educational background the tenure and the performance.
Uncertainty and Lack of Knowledge	As indicated by P8, I don't have any idea.

Teaching Loads as a Key Factor

P1, P2, P3, P4, P6, P9, and P10 emphasized that the primary determinant of salary structure was the number of teaching-loads a teacher had. The more teaching responsibilities an employee had, the higher the compensation.

“Yes, if the teacher has many teaching load the teacher will receive good compensation/salary”, as per P2.

In accordance with Hart and Staveland as cited in Tarwaka et al. (2015), workload emerges from the interplay among task demands, the working environment (utilized as a workplace), the skills, attitudes, and perceptions of workers. Operationally, workload is at times defined based on factors like the demands of tasks or the efforts invested in completing them.

Department Designation

P4 noted that the department in which an employee worked and their associated teaching loads could impact their salary. This suggested that variations might have existed within different departments or subject areas.

“Yes. It depends on where department you are in and the teaching loads,” as indicated by P4.

Money is instrumental in fulfilling physiological needs through the purchase of goods and services; it is also viewed as a measuring stick for success. Interestingly, pay is especially meaningful to people. Devoe, Pfeffer, and Lee (2013) conducted an experiment on the importance of money, finding that the importance of money increased as pay increased for labor, but the importance did not differ as pay increased when payments were randomly determined. In studying the performance effects of pay, Nyberg, Pieper, and Trevor (in press) reported that pay for-performance increased future employee performance.

Educational Qualifications and Tenure

In P5, it was mentioned that academic qualifications, educational background, tenure, and performance could also influence salary variations. This highlighted that factors beyond teaching loads could play a role in determining compensation.

“Yes, it depends on academic qualification, educational background the tenure and the performance”, according to P5.

The performance in a job is becoming more dependent on academic qualifications, ensuring individuals possess fundamental learning skills. Enhanced job performance is likely when an individual has a solid foundation in the given tasks (Faith 2014). This foundation enables effective work, innovation, and communication in the workplace. Academic qualifications offer a comprehensive life experience, exposing individuals to various employment scenarios and meeting job performance expectations. Such qualifications equip employees with the necessary skills to enhance organizational effectiveness.

Uncertainty and Lack of Knowledge

P8 expressed a lack of information or understanding regarding the factors that influenced salary structures, indicating a degree of uncertainty on this topic.

“I don’t have any idea”, stated by P8.

Table 5

Perceptions about the satisfaction and retention of the employees as influenced by their job descriptions

Themes	Excerpts
Importance of Fair Compensation	In the point of P1, by giving the right salary rate that aligns with their teaching loads. Aiding by P2, by giving enough salary and incentives based on the teacher’s work. Moreover, P3 said that, by giving the enough salary based on the duties and responsibilities. As well as supported by P4, nothing goes wrong with knowing that you get paid exactly based on your work assignment. In addition P6 indicated that, since the basic element of job satisfaction is salary, the teachers here in ICC is feel valued when they get the amount they think they deserve for the roles and responsibilities he/she have here in the institution. I feel that I am satisfied with my salary if the institution will be fair for the responsibility and duties given to me as a teacher, said by P8. As mentioned by P9, when I know to myself that I get the salary I deserve in the responsibilities and duties I have, then I can say I am satisfied. P10 stated that, it matters figure.
Salary and Incentives Alignment	According to P1, by giving the right salary rate that aligns with their teaching loads. P2 specify that by giving enough salary and incentives based on the teacher’s work. P5 also mention that by receiving the right salary and incentives that aligns with the teaching load. Besides P6 cited that since the basic element of job satisfaction is salary, the teachers here in ICC is feel valued when they get the amount they think they deserve for the roles and responsibilities he/she have here in the institution. Likewise P10 quoted that it matters figure.

Importance of Fair Compensation

P1, P2, P3, P4, P6, P8, P9, and P10 emphasized the significance of having received fair and appropriate salaries that aligned with their roles and responsibilities. In addition, P4, P6, P8, and P9 highlighted that fairness in compensation was considered essential for job satisfaction and retaining faculty and staff. A few participants highlighted personal satisfaction and a sense of value when they received salaries that they believed matched their contributions (P6, P8, P9).

“By giving enough salary and incentives based on the teacher’s work,” in the opinion of P2.

"Nothing goes wrong with knowing that you get paid exactly based on your work assignment", as believed by P4.

"Since the basic element of job satisfaction is salary, the teachers here in ICC is feel valued when they get the amount they think they deserve for the roles and responsibilities he/she have here in the institution", as emphasized by P6.

Fair compensation plays a pivotal role in the attraction and retention of skilled individuals, signaling an organization's recognition of the skills, expertise, and contributions of its workforce. When employees perceive that their dedication is acknowledged and fairly compensated, they are more likely to maintain dedication, motivation, and engagement in their roles. Fair compensation contributes to a positive work environment, elevating employee morale and resulting in heightened productivity and overall organizational prosperity. In addition to attracting top talent, providing fair compensation supports the ongoing development of employees within the organization. By investing in competitive salary packages, employers not only demonstrate appreciation but also cultivate an environment conducive to continuous learning, innovation, and loyalty. Furthermore, fair compensation serves as a catalyst for long-term employee commitment, mitigating turnover rates that can be both costly and disruptive for companies. Fostering talent through equitable compensation establishes a stable and proficient workforce, forming the bedrock for sustained growth and success within the organization (Khan, 2023).

Salary and Incentives Alignment

P1, P2, P5, P6, and P10 stressed the need for alignment between salaries and the teaching workload, advocating for appropriate incentives based on the work performed.

"By receiving the right salary and incentives that aligns with the teaching loads", as noted by P5.

The literature on human resource management and organizational behavior suggests that non-monetary incentives serve as a means of motivating employees. When organizations focus on various monetary tools, such as providing paid leave, offering bonuses for attending to employees' health and family healthcare, employees begin to perceive that the organization is actively supporting them. Consequently, monetary incentives contribute to an increase in employee motivation, resulting in enhanced job performance (Dilham et al., 2020). Further, non-monetary tools, on the other hand, are evaluated based on the leadership or the environment leaders create for their employees. While these non-monetary tools can maintain employee motivation for a certain period, a lack of appropriate incentives from organizations can negatively impact their work.

Table 6

Ensuring Fair and Transparent Relationship between Job Descriptions and Salaries

Action Area	Specific Area	Objectives	Month	Person Involved	Budget
Job Analysis and Description	Clearly defined job roles and responsibilities	- Develop comprehensive job descriptions for teachers	On-going	HR Department, Administrators, Teachers	TBD
		- Ensure alignment with educational standards	On-going		
		- Regularly update job descriptions as needed	Quarterly		
Salary Structure Development	Establishing a fair salary structure	- Research and benchmark salaries in the education sector	On-going	HR Department, Administrators	TBD
		- Consider factors such as experience and education	On-going		
		- Ensure competitiveness within the industry	On-going		
Transparent Salary Communication	Clear communication of salary information	- Provide transparent salary details in employment contracts	Monthly	HR Department, Administrators	TBD
		- Clearly outline factors affecting salary adjustments	On-going		
Performance Evaluation	Fair and consistent evaluation processes	- Establish standardized performance evaluation criteria	On-going	HR Department, Administrators	TBD
		- Encourage open communication during evaluations	On-going		

The presented table encapsulates a comprehensive strategy for fostering fairness and transparency in the relationship between job descriptions and teacher salaries. Designed to address critical aspects of employment within an educational context, the plan meticulously outlines actions, specific areas, and objectives for various key areas. The specific action delineates precise and quantifiable goals for each approach, creating a continuous schedule for execution and evaluation. Specific individuals and departments are designated with responsibilities to guarantee accountability and a concerted organizational approach. Additionally, it assigns resources, encompassing both budgetary allocations and personnel, underscoring the significance of consistent monitoring, feedback mechanisms, and adaptability to cater to individual needs. The overall strategy aims to create a fair and transparent work environment, aligning job descriptions with salaries, fostering growth, and ensuring continuous improvement within the educational institution.

Conclusions

A job description influences employee salary by delineating responsibilities, required skills, and qualifications, allowing employers to benchmark against industry standards. The complexity, impact, and location of the role further contribute to salary decisions, ensuring compensation aligns with the position's demands and market competitiveness.

In this qualitative research approach focused on a single case, an investigation was conducted into the job descriptions and salary structures of ICCBI employees. The data collected from participants underwent a comprehensive analysis using narrative analysis techniques, encompassing stages such as becoming familiar with the data, coding, identifying themes, reviewing those themes, defining and labeling them, and finally, presenting the findings in a written format. The findings of this study were organized and presented in tables numbered one (1), two (2), three (3), four (4), and five (5). In the first table, it was concluded that Immaculate Conception College of Balayan

Inc. employed a comprehensive approach to define and document job descriptions, utilizing job analysis, role and responsibility methods, qualifications and credentials, and the school manual-based method. This strategic combination ensured a thorough understanding of each position, fostering clarity of roles and expectations.

Additionally, this holistic approach to job description processes was vital for creating a transparent and harmonious work environment at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc.

In the second table, following the examination of the gathered data, the salary framework at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc. was intricately crafted, considering factors such as tenure, educational attainments, performance, teaching loads, department, experience, and collegial care. This comprehensive approach demonstrated the institution's commitment to recognizing and rewarding various aspects of employee contributions. By valuing not only academic qualifications but also experience, professional growth, and a collegial work environment, the college fostered a fair and motivating compensation system.

Moreover, this multi-faceted approach contributed to an organizational culture that appreciated and encouraged continuous professional development while ensuring equity and transparency in salary determinations at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc.,

In the third table, upon scrutinizing the data gathered from participants, the identified factors related to the job description of the employees in a way that affected salary differentiation, appropriate and aligned job descriptions, career development opportunities, and bigger duties and responsibilities.

Further, the institution's emphasis on appropriate compensation, clear job delineations, and avenues for professional growth underscored a commitment to fostering a work environment that valued and supported its workforce. Recognizing the dynamic interplay of these factors was crucial for maintaining a motivated, satisfied, and well-defined workforce within the institution.

In the fourth table, the analysis of gathered data led to the conclusion that the exploration of salary structures at the institution revealed significant factors shaping compensation. These factors encompassed teaching loads, department designation, educational qualifications, and tenure. The observed variations underscored the intricacy of the remuneration system. Recognizing the impact of these factors was essential for cultivating a work environment that is fair and equitable. Addressing these variations played a pivotal role in enhancing job satisfaction, fairness, and fostering a thriving academic community within the institution.

In the fifth table, the researchers deduced that the results underscored the crucial significance of fair compensation, harmonized with salary and incentives, in impacting job satisfaction and staff retention at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc. Acknowledging the importance of equitable remuneration was vital for nurturing a positive work environment, inspiring employees, and retaining valuable talent. The institution's dedication to aligning compensation with the contributions of its workforce represented a strategic approach that played a role in fostering overall job satisfaction, ultimately enhancing retention, and cultivating a committed and content faculty and staff community.

Recommendations

The impact of job descriptions on employee salaries is a crucial aspect that plays a pivotal role in shaping the dynamics of the employment relationship within an organization. Job descriptions serve as a foundational element for determining the scope of responsibilities, required skills, and expectations associated with a particular role. As organizations strive to attract, retain, and motivate their employees, the alignment of job roles and responsibilities with appropriate compensation becomes paramount.

Teachers are advised to actively participate in continuous self-assessment and skill development, aligning their efforts with the evolving demands specified in their job descriptions. Prioritizing the acquisition and enhancement of relevant skills not only enhances their value within the organization but also serves as a solid justification for potential

salary increments. Additionally, fostering transparent communication with supervisors and HR departments to align job descriptions with individual career aspirations can significantly contribute to a more open and equitable salary negotiation process.

Administrators should leverage the study's findings to improve the systematic, inclusive, and accurate processes for defining and documenting job descriptions. This enhancement aims to foster clarity, alignment, and overall effectiveness in job roles throughout the institution. Embracing a holistic approach will enable educational stakeholders to establish an equitable and performance-driven compensation structure, recognizing and rewarding the diverse contributions of teachers. This, in turn, creates a motivating and rewarding professional environment.

Future HR professionals are recommended to adopt an agile and adaptive approach to job descriptions, recognizing the dynamic evolution of roles over time. This involves maintaining an ongoing dialogue between employers and employees to ensure that job expectations remain current and reflective of the evolving nature of work. Implementing transparent communication channels and feedback mechanisms will foster a culture of continuous improvement, ensuring that salary structures are not only fair but also commensurate with the evolving scope and complexity of employees' responsibilities.

Future researchers are encouraged to delve deeper into understanding the impact of identified factors on job descriptions. Providing practical insights for organizations to develop more efficient and flexible roles for their workforce is crucial. Given the focus on a private institution in this study, future researchers may explore and examine how job descriptions influence the salaries of employees in diverse organizational settings, contributing to a broader understanding of this relationship.

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